
The Range of Jharkhand's Tourism

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Abstract:- Jharkhand, sometimes referred to as "The Land of Forests," is an ideal destination for those who enjoy the outdoors and animals. Hills, mountains, woods, and waterfalls are just a few of the state's many breath-taking natural features. It's a fantastic destination for vacationers who wish to spend time in the great outdoors. In addition to offering a wealth of sights and activities, including as museums, wildlife sanctuaries, and holy shrines, Jharkhand is blessed with an abundance of natural beauty. Each of these elements supports tourism in Jharkhand. In the modern world, tourism is growing in importance as a business and activity. It is also vital to the Indian economy. Jharkhand has a great deal of potential as a pilgrimage tourism destination, and the government. the state has been making every effort to support the growth of environmentally friendly travel in the region. By including the less fortunate in various tourism initiatives, it will also help them obtain employment, improve their quality of life, and increase their income. Both the area and the state will benefit from this.

Keyword: Tourism in Jharkhand, Government Initiative, GDP

I. Introduction

Both domestic and foreign travelers are referred to as tourists. The temporary travel of individuals to locations other than their usual places of employment and residence is referred to as tourism. Even in the most remote regions of the nation, it has the ability to hire a broad range of job searchers, from the unskilled to the specialized. Due to its immense potential for local economic growth, tourism has grown to be a significant socioeconomic activity. Ziffer defines tourism as visiting comparatively pristine or unspoiled natural areas with the express purpose of learning about, appreciating, and taking in the landscape, its untamed flora and fauna, as well as any lingering cultural elements. Unlike many other industries, the tourist sector is made up of several service suppliers. One of the sectors in the world with the quickest growth is tourism. Global tourism has been rising, and it is predicted that this figure will soon approach 1.5 billion. About 11% of the worldwide labor force and 10.2% of the gross domestic product are derived from the tourism business. The fact that a new job is added to this business every 2.5 seconds shows how important it is. India's tourist destinations have traditionally included seaside beaches, historical sites, and temple towns. However, the nature of tourism has changed in recent years. Destinations for pleasure, nature, and history are becoming increasingly important. Eco-tourism has emerged as a major draw for travelers in recent years. Within India, tourism is expanding quickly and has become more important economically. In 2015, tourism contributed Rs. 8.31 lakh crore, or 6.3%, to the country's GDP and created 37.315 million jobs, or 8.7% of all occupations. By 2025, the industry is expected to earn Rs. 8.36 lakh crore, or 7.2% of GDP, growing at an average annual rate of 7.5%. In 2015, 8.02 million foreign visitors entered India, representing a 4.4% growth rate, up from 7.68 million in 2014—a 10.2% increase over 2013. In 2012, 1036.35 million domestic tourists visited all states and Union Territories, a 16.5% increase from 2011. India was rated 16th in the world for tourism receipts in the globe in 2012, and seventh among nations in Asia and the Pacific.

As a state, Jharkhand is abundantly endowed with natural resources and possesses a rich cultural legacy. It's a stunning state with verdant forests, fascinating wildlife, mesmerizing waterfalls, superb handicrafts, expansive bodies of water, entrancing folk and classical music, and most importantly, friendly, peaceful people. The state of Jharkhand is a popular travel destination because of its enormous biodiversity, beautiful climate, rich cultural and historical legacy, sites of worship, and ethnic characteristics. The proliferation of hotels and restaurant facilities in the state, the creation of new tourist destinations, the enhancement of already popular tourist spots, and increased infrastructure have all contributed to Jharkhand's tourism industry's recent notable expansion.

Chief Minister Hemans Soren announced the policy's launch on Saturday, stating that of Employment, economic expansion, sustainable development, and the preservation of art, culture, and legacy would be some of the important areas in this. Since the days of British administration, Jharkhand has been regarded as a mineral resource. It served as a hub for mineral extraction. However, nobody is shocked by the state's tribal population's backwardness. With this philosophy, we are now turning our attention from extraction to attraction," Soren stated. The new policy also addresses issues related to religion, the environment, culture, the countryside, adventure,

wellness, and mining tourism. In addition to bolstering the Jharkhand Tourism Development Corporation, it also intends to establish tourism economic zones and a tourism development board. Jharkhand Development Commissioner Arun Kumar Singh highlighted the potential for ecotourism, saying: "People can unwind in the woods. With two airports located in Dhanbad and Deoghar, top-notch infrastructure, and no safety or security concerns, Jharkhand is well-equipped. Organizing buyer-seller meetings to promote tourism products, running public awareness campaigns, especially among tribal people, and providing stakeholder training on tourism promotion, marketing, and related services are some of the primary strategies mentioned in the new policy.

1. Investment avenues for development of tourism industry in Jharkhand

In the tourist sector, build-operate-transfer (BOT), build-own-operate-transfer (BOOT), and built-lease-transfer (BLT) models are to be promoted for public-private partnerships (PPPs). To support the industry, foreign investments and technological cooperation with foreign investors would be implemented. The government wants to promote private investment and involvement in tourism infrastructure projects from both domestic and international sources. The new tourism policy calls for strategic partnerships with private tour operators to establish travel packages and services, modernize tourist information centres, and carry out in-depth analyses of each district's potential for tourism. "Jharkhand is a cultural hub and a model of sustainable living—nature's hidden jewel. Its natural beauty and rich cultural heritage have enormous unrealized potential to draw tourists. These might make the state a popular travel destination, according to Soren. The nation also intends to launch the Jharkhand tourist Home Stay Scheme, a bed-and-breakfast program modelled after "Incredible India" run by the state's tourist government. Following the announcement of the new policy, a teaser for the promotional series "Postcards from Jharkhand" was released, showcasing the state's natural beauty and rich cultural heritage. The National Geographic channel and the Jharkhand government worked together to produce the series. "Jharkhand is a cultural hub and a model of sustainable living—nature's hidden jewel. Its natural beauty and rich cultural heritage have enormous unrealized potential to draw tourists. These might make the state a popular travel destination, according to Soren. Additionally, the state intends to launch the Jharkhand Tourism Home Stay Scheme, which is modeled after the "Incredible India" bed-and-breakfast program run by the tourism ministry.

1.1 Improving connectivity

The policy suggests giving road permits to tour operators and aggregators in order to improve connectivity within the state. The Union Railway Ministry will be convinced to enlarge the state's railway network by the state government. By guaranteeing that the current small fees or tariffs to entice airlines to utilize state-owned landing facilities won't be raised during this policy period, it has provided relief to airlines.

1.2 Benefits offered

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1.3 Benefits offered

To encourage investment in the state's tourist industry, the government is offering a single-window system, a 20–25% capital investment subsidy (up to Rs 10 crore), and a reimbursement of 75% of net goods and services tax paid over a five-year period. Additional incentives include a five-year holding tax exemption, reimbursement for stamp and utility duties, and a thirty percent rebate up to Rs 5 lakh for captive power generation. One of the five-year fiscal incentives is a 50% interest subsidy, up to Rs 20 lakh. In addition, the government will make special accommodations for women, disabled individuals, ex-service members, scheduled castes, and scheduled tribes. Regarding the advantages provided, Soren stated: "We have been seeing mining and mineral wealth for a long time. Because of Jharkhand's abundant natural resources, several states are prospering even now, while Jharkhand continues to face numerous issues. We created this policy in order to hasten the economic growth of rural areas for this reason. Speaking on how COVID-19 affected the travel and tourist sector, he stated: "A lot of individuals lost a lot of money during the epidemic, especially those who worked in the travel and tourism sector. They will benefit

from this new policy. "With exclusive access to uranium, gold, bauxite, and coal mines, the unexplored state of Jharkhand has a huge potential to be tapped and used for the state's development," stated Singh.

1.4 Tourist protection

Ex-servicemen will be brought in to form a security force. Legislation enabling the tourism trade has also been enacted to prohibit service providers from taking advantage of tourists.

2. Background

Kumar & Mishra (2018), The tourism industry in Jharkhand has been greatly influenced by the state's distinctive natural beauty and tribal culture. An obvious shift and influence on socio-economic factors has resulted from the increase of tourists visiting the state of Jharkhand. The state is well-liked for tourism because of its natural beauty. The primary source of appeal for many significant tourist destinations is domestic travel. The purpose of the article is to determine the effects of tourism characteristics such as socio-cultural development, infrastructure development, economic development, cost of living, and environment using primary data gathered from the replies of people of six popular tourist destinations in Jharkhand. The opinions of the responder were determined using a five-point Likert scale. The aforementioned data was analyzed in order to determine the influence of several aspects of tourism on Jharkhand tourist prospects.

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(2017) Prajapati et al. Tourism has grown to be an indisputable aspect of contemporary life in recent years. It is a well-established and important component of global economic development. Positive outcomes include the development of mutual understanding, multicultural interactions, and jobs and income. A significant contributor to employment, foreign exchange earnings, income, and tax revenue is tourism. With this background in mind, yes. This essay aims to investigate the economic effects of tourism within the framework of Jharkhand's socioeconomic development. Jharkhand is a stunning Indian state that is well-known for its lush forests, diverse wildlife, captivating waterfalls, exquisite handicrafts, expansive water bodies, mesmerizing folk and classical music, and, most importantly, its friendly and peaceful citizens. The state of Jharkhand is a top tourist destination because of its enormous biodiversity, temperate temperature, rich cultural and historical legacy, sites of worship, and ethnic variety. The creation of new tourist attractions, the enhancement of already popular ones, fair infrastructure amenities, and the robust expansion of the state's hotel and restaurant business have all contributed to Jharkhand's tourism industry's recent rise. This is evident from the fact that the number of visitors to the state, both domestic and foreign, is rising, as is the amount of money coming in from their spending. Because to the state's over 360% increase in foreign visitors, Jharkhand has become a more popular travel destination in India. overseas in the years 2010–2011. Therefore, in order to support tourism-related activities and ensure the state's steady and sustainable growth, the government should develop plans and policies in this regard.

Hussain & Ahmad (2017), India is one of the numerous nations and places where tourism is a significant source of revenue. In actuality, it has a direct impact on international relations in addition to the social, cultural, educational,

and economic spheres of every given national society. It injects significant sums of money into the local economy by covering the cost of the goods and services that visitors require. It is a powerful method of capital transfer, especially in the liberalization and globalization age, from rich to impoverished regions. Additionally, it generates job possibilities in the tourism-related service sector of the economy. India's tourism industry has grown rapidly in recent years, and Hazaribagh (Jharkhand) is one of the among the top travel locations for both domestic and international tourists. Rich in natural and cultural heritage, Jharkhand and particularly Hazaribagh have up till now been undiscovered and underdeveloped regions. In addition to this, the region has the ability to draw tourists due to its abundance of handicrafts and fine art, as well as several tribal celebrations. This report investigates Hazaribagh's tourism growth potential. It also looks at how the growth of tourism in Hazaribagh might benefit the region's economically and socially marginalized population, especially the tribal people living there.

Sengupta & Hazra (2013), Large neighboring attractions provide both benefits and revenue for a great number of local communities in emerging regions and beyond. The interaction between the local people (host) communities, their local mining heritage sites, and legacy tourism infrastructure is examined in this article as an example of the complex part's capabilities. India's Jharkhand state is utilized to highlight the potential of its cultural legacy, the importance of local involvement, and the management of heritage tourism in developing nations. It also provides some thoughts on how marketing and planning techniques for the tourism industry may support small-scale local tourism businesses, benefiting both the study's hosts and visitors. This essay concentrates on the crucial problems related to boosting revenue from a tourism perspective. It makes advantage of a data group of visitors (both local and foreign) between 2005 and 2010 in order to assess how their experiences in Jharkhand's tourism areas have changed over time. The statistics were computed using the PCT (percentage) approach. The outcomes positively affect how assumptions are adjusted under various conditions.

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2011's Chatterjee et al. The goal of this project is to develop and market tourism in Jharkhand, India. Tourism is a significant driver of the local economy, sociocultural shifts, and way of life of the people who live near Jharkhand's tourist attractions. This study aims to investigate the primary reason for which tourists, both local and foreign, come to this state. A pilot survey has been carried out at various Jharkhand tourist attractions in order to determine

an efficient marketing plan to boost Jharkhand tourism. It has been noted that this is because of how tourism has grown, which raises the level of living for locals and improves municipal utilities like transportation, sanitation, and communication. This research highlights highlights the numerous concerns and issues surrounding Jharkhand's tourism industry. This essay also emphasizes the importance of a comprehensive marketing plan for promoting tourism in the state.

According to Jeyaseelan (2009), The tourism, eco-tourism, and remote sensing industries have been using geographic information systems (GIS), aerial photography, light detection and ranging (LIDAR), and other remote sensing techniques more and more in the past few years to develop new presentation and proposal strategies that will optimize tourism's promotional appeal and its main assets—which include a distinctive landscape and scenery, an impressive cultural heritage, and a variety of sports facilities and other tourist amenities. For guests to obtain any information about their preferred area, resorts, hotels, property owners, tour operators, and travel agencies use satellite photos, GIS mapping, and 3D visualization.

Pusa (2009), This study investigates how the Dalma Wildlife Sanctuary's ecotourism development is seen or felt by the local populace. In order to conduct this poll, the researcher visited the sanctuary and spoke with locals there about their opinions about the growth of ecotourism in the area. For this study, 210 replies in total were examined. Factor analysis and descriptive analysis were used to analyze the data that had been gathered. The results of the MANOVA test show that respondents' opinions regarding the growth of ecotourism in their community vary depending on their age and gender. The findings show that in recent years, ecotourism has been viewed as a tool for development. Because it has increased social welfare and educational attainment as well as provided greater economic opportunities, its good effects have outweighed its negative ones. There has been a rise in Despite the fact that local respondents cited traffic issues within the sanctuary as one of the biggest negative effects, they are proud of the ecotourism industry's steady growth over the past few years and are eager to support further initiatives to further the sector's development. It is discussed what needs to be studied further.

Patil and Chand (2007), A key component in the growth of niche tourism and destinations has been gastronomy. There is evidence in the literature that there is a connection between gastronomy and tourism, however gastronomy has only been briefly used to display and serve local cuisine to visitors. For several tourism market groups, gastronomy tourism can be a draw. Owing to India's varied topography, not every state can use the tried-and-true 4S formula—sun, sand, sea, and sex—to boost travel. However, gastronomy tourism might be a special tool for the growth of tourism. The 286th State of the Indian Union, Jharkhand, is home to tribal cuisine, which has the potential to attract both domestic and foreign travellers in addition to those with specific interests. Despite Jharkhand's separation from Bihar on November 15, 2000, the region's rich history and culture date back thousands of years beyond its current boundaries. While the culinary trends of neigh boring states, including as West Bengal, Orissa, Bihar, and Chhattisgarh, have an influence on the regional specialties, many native dishes and drinks are still made in their unique ways, offering gastronomy travelers a chance to indulge while also learning.

II. Places to Visit in Jharkhand

One of the greatest locations in Jharkhand to visit is Ranchi, which provides you with a breathtaking view of some of India's top waterfalls. Known as "the City of Waterfalls," it serves as Jharkhand's capital. One location that is so abundant in natural resources is Ranchi, which has earned the moniker "Manchester of the East." Encircled by tranquil hills and mountains and teeming with divine waterfalls, Ranchi never lets its visitors down, providing them with the most unforgettable vacation experience.

Some of the popular tourist attractions in Ranchi are:

- Hundru Falls
- Dassam Falls
- Jonha Falls
- Panch Gagh Falls
- Birsa Zoological Park

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- Ranchi Lake
 - Kanke Dam
 - Jagannath Temple
 - Nakshatra Van
 - Sun Temple
 - Pahari Mandir
 - Rock Garden
 - Deer Park

Jamshedpur

India's Steel City Jharkhand's main city, Jamshedpur, is home to Tata Steel, India's first privately owned iron and steel firm. Many tourist attractions in this well-planned city provide visitors with an amazing experience; in particular, nature enthusiasts can find solace in discovering the area's natural beauty. Jamshedpur, also referred to as an industrial city, was established by the renowned industrialist and Tata Group founder Jamsedji Nusserwanji Tata. The city is surrounded by lush vegetation and has a ton of things to offer visitors who want to enjoy a fun-filled vacation.

Some of the great attractions in Jamshedpur include:

- Dalma Hills
- Jubilee Park
- Jubilee Lake
- Jayanti Sarovar
- Tata Steel Zoological Park
- Tribal Culture Centre
- Hudco Lake
- Bhuvneshwari Temple

Hazaribagh

Because of its beautiful weather, excellent hills, and an abundance of flora, this scenic location greatly enhances Jharkhand's wildlife tourism industry. At an elevation of 2019 feet, Hazaribagh is a biodiverse area renowned for its health resort. Hazaribagh, as its name implies, means "city of thousand gardens," but the city is home to many temples, hills, waterfalls, and wildlife sanctuaries that provide visitors with an enjoyable experience.

Some of the best places to visit here are:

- Canary Hill
- Hazaribagh Wildlife Sanctuary
- Hazaribagh National Park
- Isko Village
- Suryakund

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- Rajarappa temple
 - Urwan Tourist Complex
 - Konar Dam

Deoghar

When it comes to religious tourism, Deoghar is among the top destinations in Jharkhand. Thanks to its immense natural beauty and serene surroundings, Deoghar, home to numerous Hindu temples primarily dedicated to Lord Shiva, guarantees its visitors a pretty pleasant holiday. There is so much to see and do in Deoghar that visitors come here in big numbers to take in its unique beauty from all over the nation. Deoghar is also well-known for its historic temples, such as Baba Baidyanath, which is regarded as one of India's twelve "Jyotirlingas" and offers visitors seeking tranquility and calm a heavenly retreat.

Some important places of worship & tourist attractions in Deoghar include:

- Basukinath
- Trikuta Hills
- Satsanga Ashram
- Harila Jori
- Shivganga
- Rikhia Yogashram
- Jaisar Children's Park
- Nandan Pahar
- Kathikund
- Kundeshwari
- Ajgaibinath
- Hathi Pahar

Giridih

Founded in 1972, Giridih was formerly a part of Hazaribagh but is now an independent city. It is well-known for its mining towns and rolling hills covered in dense forests, including a huge plantation of bamboo, sal trees, mahua, and palash. Giridih, sometimes referred to as the "Land of Hills," is a popular destination for Jain pilgrims and is frequently referred to as "The land of Jain Pilgrims." Giridih is a popular destination for pilgrims and environment enthusiasts due to its numerous Jain temples and other Jain structures and locations. Giridih's picturesque hills, valleys, dams, and temples all contribute to Jharkhand's tourism industry.

Major tourist destinations in Giridih include:

- Parashnath Hills
- Usri Fall
- Khandoli Park and Dam
- Madhuvan
- Jharkhandi Dham

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- Harihar Dham
 - Langta Baba Samadhi Sthal
 - Surya Temple
 - Devari Temple

Sahibganj

This less well-known location is actually rather beautiful; families, kids, couples, and lone travelers like to favor it for hiking, photography, and sightseeing. Whether you visit in the summer, monsoon, or winter, this charming city is a great place to go because of its comfortable climate and beautiful surroundings. Travelers from far-off places come to Sahibganj to take in the natural beauty that envelops the city and to see a few historically significant locations. Sahibganj doesn't have many attractions, however if you want to have a great time while visiting this beautiful city, you should surely go to the following places:

- Mary's Church
- Rajmahal
- Mangalhat
- Moti waterfall
- Shivgadi Temple
- Bhagwa Kuan
- Shukravasini Temple
- Teliagarhi Fort
- Binduvasini Temple
- Raksisthan Temple

Dhanbad

Dhanbad, also referred to as the "Coal Capital of India," is one of the nation's fastest-growing towns, providing a wealth of opportunities for visitors to take in the state's unique beauty. The well-known mining city in Jharkhand is home to more attractions than only coal mines. Encircled by charming valleys and verdant forests, Dhanbad provides vistas of impressive dams, revitalizing lakes, and temples—which continue to be a primary draw here. Many pilgrims travel to Dhanbad to see Dalmi, a sacred location housing the idols of Nandi, Lord Shiva, Goddess Durga, and Lord Ganesha. There are numerous Buddhist and Jain landmarks in the city, which provide visitors with a more enlightening vacation.

III. Jharkhand Tourism

The Jharkhand Tourism Policy's main objectives are to beautify locations like Deoghar, Parasnath, Madhuban, and Itkhori and to provide municipal facilities. Additionally, the state will establish religious tourism units with the goal of enhancing the potential of religious tourism. In addition, plans are being made to build eco-circuits and offer lodging to visitors in forest rest houses and tree plantations as part of its efforts to promote eco-tourism. There is a drive to host conferences, food festivals, and interstate cultural exchange programs to highlight the dynamic and diversified culture of the state and introduce tourists to Jharkhand's magnificent and sparkling society. Additionally, efforts are being undertaken to resolve conflicts between rural and urban regions. To increase the potential of rural tourism, such activities will include promoting regional cuisines, exhibiting rural life, and publicizing and promoting tourist-specific settlements. In this way, the Rural Tourism Subcommittee and Village Tourism Committees (VTC) will be formed. By providing plenty of flexibility for modern travelers' tastes and preferences, the Policy also aims to satisfy their needs. It has been suggested to promote adventure tourist activities like rock

climbing, sea sports, paragliding, and gliding. In addition, annual adventure sports competitions must be planned, and legal frameworks guaranteeing safety requirements must be established. Activities including water sports would be developed and expanded to the State's many bodies of water, including Tilaiya, Kelaghagh, Kanke dam, Hatia dam, Massanjore, Chandil, and Pataratu. Getalsud and so forth. Through the expansion of tourism units under the umbrella of wellness tourism, the strategy hopes to establish Jharkhand as a destination for "Rest and Recuperate." There will be thrilling escape choices available for anybody seeking a respite from the fast-paced, daily life in the metropolis. Another concept that is gaining popularity on a national and international level to highlight the state's mineral resources is mining tourism.

IV. Government Initiative

The State Government is adamant that the growth of the tourism industry would not only create a plethora of direct and indirect job possibilities, but also accelerate economic development by increasing the standard of living for everybody. Because of this, Jharkhand's State Government has designated tourism as an industry. The Tourism Department's persistent efforts have produced positive outcomes. The table below illustrates the rise in the number of tourists, both foreign and domestic, visiting the state.

Source: Ministry of Tourism, Jharkhand

Table I- Table showing the number of tourists visiting Jharkhand

Sl. No.	Period	National	International
1.	Nov.2000 to Dec. 2000	23,991	172
2	Jan. 2001 to Dec. 2001	450447	3111
3	Jan.2002 to Dec.2002	346830	2322
4	Jan.2003 to Dec.2003	386506	3141
5	Jan.2004 to Dec.2004	477507	4620
6	Jan.2005 to Dec.2005	2164483	5766
7	Jan.2006 to Dec.2006	2138685	3180
8	Jan.2007 to Dec.2007	4906394	4004
9	Jan.2007 to Dec.2007	6030028	5803
10	Jan.2008 to Dec.2008	7606160	8303
11	Jan.2009 to Dec.2009	6430083	8244
12	Jan.2010 to Dec.2010	6800000	15695
13	Jan.2011 to Dec.2011	1079600	72467
14	Jan.2012 to Dec.2012	1256582	31909
15	Jan.2013 to Dec.2013	2456580	45995
16	Jan.2014 to Dec.2014	3360000	154731

It is clear from the above table that Jharkhand has seen an increase in the number of visitors, both domestic and foreign. Only 23991 national visitors visited in 2000; by 2014, that number has risen to 3360000. In a same vein, it is evident that Jharkhand saw 172 foreign tourists in 2000 and 154731 in 2014.

V. Conclusion

Jharkhand, also referred to as "The Land of Forests," is the perfect place for people who have a strong respect for the natural environment. Numerous picturesque natural elements, such as waterfalls, hills, mountains, and forests, may be found in this state. It's a terrific place for anyone who want to spend their holiday exploring the great outdoors. The state of Jharkhand is home to a multitude of tourism attractions, such as museums, religious monuments, and animal protection areas, in addition to its abundance of natural beauty. All of these things are beneficial to Jharkhand's tourism sector. One of the most important businesses and pastimes in the modern world is tourism, which is growing quickly. An important part of the Indian economy. Jharkhand offers a great deal of unrealized potential for eco-friendly pilgrimage tourist destinations, and the state government has been making every effort to support the growth of eco-friendly tourism in the region. It will be feasible for the less fortunate members of society to obtain jobs, raise their level of living, and improve their financial situation by including them in various tourism activities. This will be advantageous to the state and the local community alike.

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